

IMPROVING THE TRAINING SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION BASED ON INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11194875>

It is certainly not a secret that in the era of globalization, which is developing in new Uzbekistan, great work is being done to further develop science, to educate our youth as possessors of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, and to create a competitive economy. It is no secret to all of us that the declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Youth and Business Support" in our country in order to raise it to a new, modern level is a practical expression of attention to the human factor.

The flow of innovative technologies has spread rapidly in almost all developed countries and is currently being successfully adopted in many countries. The idea of full management of the basis of technologyization of education was established in order to improve the independent educational process and its efficiency, and to guarantee that learners achieve the planned educational results under the given conditions and within the time allotted.

In the higher education system of our country, using electronic information and educational resources, improving the methodical support of subjects, forming and developing the competence of students, wide-scale and mass use of multimedia and information and communication technologies in training are the most urgent issues of today.

The main components of the educational environment are undoubtedly important nowadays in the process of forming the digital information educational environment and its integration into the general educational system, in the development of the electronic education system. Creating a digital information learning environment is an important factor in the formation of a person-oriented educational environment. It is based on the identification of his personal abilities as a subject of knowledge and activity, and in turn, on the recognition of the right of everyone to choose the direction of his development by studying alternative forms of education. Based on this educational theory, the authors V.P. Lebedeva, V.A. Orlov, V.A. Yasvin and others emphasize the growing role of differentiation and individualization of education, at the same time, they explain this role in a different way than previously accepted, taking into account the specific characteristics of modern society.

In modern conditions, the most optimal way to increase the effectiveness of education is to organize training using innovative methods. So, what are innovative methods? What didactic possibilities do they have? What results are guaranteed by the appropriate and purposeful use of interactive methods in the educational process? We will briefly touch on such questions below.

Currently, the concept of "innovation" is very widely used. The word innovation is of English origin that means "innovation", that is, it is defined as changing the internal structure of a system. Innovation is an important part of practice and theory, and it is a system of actions of social subjects aimed at improving the qualities of a socio-cultural object.

Innovations are relevant, important, new approaches formed in one system. They are born on the basis of initiatives and innovations, and will be promising for the development of educational content. It also has a positive effect on the development of the education system as a whole. Innovation is the end result of technology, forms and methods in a certain field of activity or production, a new approach to solving a problem, or the use of a new technological process which leads to greater success than before.

Currently, the countries with developed information and communication technologies include: the USA, China, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, South Korea, Great Britain, and Singapore. Information and communication technologies are developing in Uzbekistan, like the countries of the world. After the application of information technologies in our daily life, many opportunities are created for ordinary people. It is necessary to adapt the educational system to the digital generation through mass and effective use of innovative educational technologies and didactic models based on information and communication technologies. At the same time, it is necessary to actively use the approach based on research in the educational process, and with this, it is possible to develop the skills of students in scientific research and to form their creative abilities and creative thinking based on IT competence.

Information and communication technologies are not a solution to all problems in the education system, but a means of making lectures and seminars informative and interactive for the digital generation. It should also be noted that students retain the main role in the interactive learning process focused on the needs of students.

The introduction of modern information technologies into the field of education in higher education institutions allows students to qualitatively change the content, methods and organizational forms of education. The goal of these

technologies in education is to increase the intellectual capabilities of students in the information society, as well as to individualize, humanize, intensify and improve the quality of education at all stages of the educational system.

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